

PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE

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ABSTRACT

The primary goals of physical education for young children in preschool settings, including in the home, are to help them become strong and healthy, to tame their bodies, and to correctly arrange their education and upbringing. Preschoolers' health-improvement activities are the most fundamental physical education tasks, and they involve safeguarding a child's life, enhancing his health, developing his ability to defend himself by training his body, and boosting his resistance to various diseases. Children in the preschool years get feedback and feedback on physical education.

Introduction. Children receive movement instruction during physical education under the direct supervision of the teacher, as well as during their independent activities while he is watching. The development of the child's cognitive, volitional, and emotional energies as well as the formation of his practical movement skills occur when teaching movement activity. Teaching techniques have a targeted impact on a child's senses, thinking, gradually developing worldview, moral characteristics, and motor activity that is beneficial for their general physical and mental development. Preschoolers participate in planned physical activities, action games, and educational programs that are chosen based on state education and program criteria. In the educational process, adults expose kids to goal-oriented activity. Its content also includes the experience of mastering actions that serve to develop and improve.

When working with preschool children, it is imperative to take into account their age characteristics, certain knowledge that hangs in the child's conscious movement activity; the unity of knowledge about the methods of activity that teach the child to actions, about the skills and abilities of activity and their implementation forms components based on work processes. One of the parts is the experience of creative activity. A person who has not been taught to think independently since childhood and assimilates everything after being given Ready, cannot show the qualities given to him by nature. Therefore, society cannot fully look at the learning of the younger generation to creative activity. In the process of educating movement activities, adults (parents, caregivers), taking into account the physiological features of the development of children, put new movement tasks in front of them.

The fact that the child is increasingly able to solve new movement tasks in the process of exercise, and the great opportunities that arise in connection with this, change the character

and quality of actions. What is very characteristic of this age period is that in the process of teaching new exercises, as if one turns into a new quality. The child's gait is completely different at the first time and at the end of the second year. This phenomenon can be represented as a didactic denial of the old thing of the novelty, an objective condition for all development and resolution of conflicts, a moving factor. Development in each area cannot go without denying the forms of residence that preceded it. Such a complex development process is non-stop in the interconnection of external and internal conditions. Overcoming difficulties and solving new tasks creates a positive emotional mood in the child. This goal achieved is due to new muscle sensations according to the educator's assessment. Strengthening the changes that have arisen serves to awaken the desire for even higher achievements. This complex process must always be under the supervision of an educator. On the one hand, it is necessary to ensure that the child understands the task of a new action, and on the other hand, it is necessary to instill in the child independence and its implementation on the basis of existing real action opportunities and emerging interests, emotions, enthusiasm.

Physical education requires a child to focus, develop an active imagination, active thinking, and memory. For instance, if the educational process is enjoyable and filled with emotion, it will likely be emotional; if the educator illustrates the movement pattern and the students imitate it, it will likely be figurative; and if the task of consistently carrying out all the exercise's components will be consistent. Education must be free in order for this to happen; only then can the exercises be carried out deliberately and autonomously. Moral education in teaching children is directly related to the formation of a child's spiritual sense and consciousness, the development of his moral and volitional qualities, such as high-quality and mutual assistance, goal-striving, honesty, fairness. The whole process of teaching correct movements fosters aesthetic sensations in children.

Beautiful movements that kids gradually pick up, neatly lined up, age-appropriate game graphics that express themselves creatively, lyrical game words, game begins, and counting are all things that help kids develop an aesthetic sense. The outward embellishment of children's and teachers' clothing, physical education textbooks, etc., is quite significant. The way that education is organized allows us to give kids the skills they need to participate in labor movements. The teacher frequently makes it clear that it is the students' responsibility to maintain their physical education supplies tidy and orderly. First off, the duty officers are concerned about this and have already placed the appropriate equipment. At the same time, they also pay attention to the layout of the subject and inventory so that all children are comfortable to use. Children wash balloons, balls, etc. from time to time and wipe large appliances. At such an event, all caregivers participate under the guidance of an educator. Thus, in the process of teaching actions, children develop mental abilities, moral and aesthetic feelings, a conscious attitude to their activities and, in connection with this, a desire for a goal, organization are formed. All this is the implementation of a general approach to the educational process in interaction. This process serves the formation of a comprehensively developed personality.

Specific aspects of young children's growth and physical education assignments. The major objective of education and preschool education is to grow the younger generation into a healthy, fully-fledged individual based on the idea of independence and to get them ready for

school. The primary goals of preschool education and upbringing are the physical, mental, and spiritual growth of the children as well as their preparation for formal education (school) on the basis of national and universal values while taking into account their button capacity, interest, needs, and abilities.

Tasks of physical education of children of preschool age. The only goal in all the bogies of the physical education system is: to carry out the work of preparing children for life, Labor and defense of the motherland. The tasks of physical education of children of preschool age are given taking into account their age characteristics. In preschool institutions, there are the following tasks of physical education:

- Health-improving functions.
- Educational tasks.
- Educational tasks. health-improving functions.
- Preservation of life and strengthening of taxation.

In the period of technical development of Physical Education, great importance is attached to physical education and sports. Because, in the era of technical progress, humanity is freed from physical labor and suffers the most dangerous disease "low Moment", which leads to a disease of the vascular system. Therefore, the law on "Physical Education and Sports" issued by the state in recent years and the decree and program "for the healthy generation" are evidence of the moral and physical development of children, their health, labor e var, the right to be happy. Therefore, it is important that we use physical education tools for the physical and comprehensive development of children.

Introducing physical activity to preschoolers methodology Gymnastics is a Specially Selected System of Exercises that profoundly impacts a person's body, strengthens key physiological functions, and fosters harmonic growth. Gymnastics exercises help build important movement skills, beautiful and accurate motions, and the five main physical attributes of agility, speed, strength, endurance, and flexibility. Gymnastics is practiced beginning in early childhood and is continued throughout an individual's life.

Action games are the main means of physical education. Action games have a creative effect on the physical development of children's movement activity, the formation of movement skills and physical qualities, the strengthening of health by increasing the functional activity of the body and enhancing the feelings of emotional cheerfulness. The effect of socialization achieved when performing action games is inextricably linked with positive emotions that arise in the process of children's game activity and have a good effect on the child's psyche. However, the options are necessary not only in order to maintain the interest of children in relation to him, but also in order to improve pedagogical tasks-actions, somewhat complex game actions, change the conditions of the game situation to fulfill the rules of need to educate their child's physical qualities. They require a certain mental and physical strength from children and at the same time increased heating in relation to the game.

Physical exercises and sports in the organization of children's movement activities, sports games and exercises are given a large place. Walking in skiing, skating, sledding, cycling, walking in a sports Roller, as well as swimming, belong to sports exercises. All of them contribute to the strengthening of the main muscle groups, the development of bone, cardiovascular, respiratory and nervous systems. In addition, in the process of training,

children develop physical qualities, as well as rhythm, coordination of movements, the qualification of molting in space. Cycling, skating develop vestibular stability.

In Conclusion, the forms of Organization of physical education in children's kindergarten physical education exercises are the main form of regular training of children for physical exercises. The exercises serve to educate individuals who are cheerful, disciplined, able to act well in the environment, act quickly and confidently according to the set task, guided by the goal, and are also able to show moral qualities and creativity. The importance of training consists in the formation of the embodiment of the culture of actions, the regular implementation of health-improving, educational and educational tasks.

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